

Enriching Model Based Systems Engineering with Interoperability through Master Data: A Case Study of High Speed 2 (UK) and Flemish Tunnel Standard (Belgium)

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Abstract

Model Based Systems Engineering (MBSE) is described as a technical approach that creates domain models as the primary way for information exchange. MBSE is a powerful solution to the multidisciplinary challenges posed by large-scale infrastructure projects. This includes the need to collaborate in complex, project-based organisational structures. With numerous collaborating parties involved throughout the supply chain, there is an increasing demand to access consistent, timely and reliable information.

The increasing digital maturity in the infrastructure construction sector requires a more efficient way of sharing information that could be facilitated by an MBSE approach. Due to differences in technology and semantics, however, Systems Engineering implementation throughout the project phases is hindered and requires the costly and time-consuming development of point-to-point interfaces to exchange data on projects. Thus, there is a need to enrich the MBSE approach to increase interoperability by enabling stakeholders to share the meaning of their data.

Ensuring quality and satisfaction of project demands depends heavily on accurate Requirements Management (RM). To illustrate, this paper presents two case studies: the High Speed 2 (HS2) rail construction project in the UK, and the Flemish Tunnel Standard in Belgium. The case studies review the developments, benefits, and challenges of an Object Type approach for RM. The Object Type approach on HS2 takes the form of a project requirement library standardising assets and work packages throughout the project. The Flemish Tunnel Standards uses an Object Type Library (OTL)

based on Linked Data techniques to standardise information across projects and software applications. This paper discusses the key benefits of MBSE on complex multi-stakeholder projects and provides insights on the practical application of OTLs to aid collaboration in Systems Engineering. The Key benefits include cost savings and the increased interoperability, consistency, and reliability of systems.

Introduction

Over the past few years, Model-Based Systems Engineering (MBSE) has gained significant momentum, offering enhanced communication, reduced ambiguity, and optimised Systems Engineering processes [Campo 2022]. MBSE has notable advantages such as improved Verification & Validation (V&V) Capability, Consistency, Reasoning, and Risk & Error Manageability. Researchers have focused on augmenting MBSE for interoperability through Master Data, defined as standardised data types.

The use of manual communication for Requirements Management (RM) in the construction industry often results in slow processing times, errors, and reliability issues [Bazuin 2023]. Although software applications have potential benefits for RM and V&V, the lack of standardisation and mechanisms for information exchange continue to pose challenges.

To address interoperability challenges in Systems Engineering, the use of Linked Data (a set of technological principles for machine-readable data on the Web) was proposed as solution for cross-context Master Data Libraries [Van Ruijven 2015]. Libraries, in this context, are accessible repositories of standardised information for projects, which can be accessed by applications.

In recent years, the infrastructure construction industry put this into practice, improving information exchange using Linked Data on two levels by:

- (1) Developing core ontologies to align conceptual information structures at the highest level, such as the EN 17632-2021 Building information modelling (BIM) - Semantic modelling and linking (SML) standard [CEN 2021], and
- (2) Introducing extended domain-specific ontologies, such as the Conference of European Directors of Roads (CEDR) Object Type Library “INTERLINK” [CEDR 2018], to ensure Master Data alignment at the business level.

Recent advancements in Master Data-enhanced MBSE have demonstrated effectiveness in knowledge representation, sharing and coherent management. This is done by adding context to MBSE data by means of ontologies [Yang 2019].

Domain-specific ontologies containing Object Type information are referred to as Object Type Libraries (OTLs). They offer a repository of standardised information about object types for projects and applications to refer to. The Netherlands has emerged as a European leader in integrating Master Data into MBSE using Linked Data technologies [LDAC 2022]. The Dutch government-owned power company, TenneT, successfully employed them for EU-303 asset information exchange and project requirements management.

This paper aims to illustrate how MBSE has been enhanced using Linked Data techniques to bolster interoperability in large-scale infrastructure projects. By examining two case studies—the High Speed 2 (HS2) rail construction project in the UK and the Flemish Tunnel Standard in Belgium—this paper

will underscore the advancements, benefits, and challenges associated with employing a project requirement library and Object Type Library based on Linked Data techniques in Systems Engineering. To ensure a structured analysis between the cases, the implementation of MBSE has been assessed across the Process, Method, Tools and Environment of each project [Martin 1994].

Approach

High Speed 2

Starting in 2017, the High Speed 2 (HS2) railway is the UK’s flagship transport project. It has created over 34,000 jobs and 170 miles of new high-speed line are currently under construction in over 350 sites. To deliver this flagship project, HS2 is being delivered in multiple contracts (e.g., civils works, rail systems). These contracts are then split geographically along the full HS2 line. This case study refers to only one of the portions of civils works being delivered.

The 80 kilometres of civil infrastructure work aims to deliver over 4,000 civil assets. It includes a variety of Object Types such as Bridging Structures, Tunnels, Earthworks and Highway Features. Each of these Object Types have multiple instances, for example, there are 15 viaduct assets in the scope. To achieve the required level of self-assurance, the contractor is required to establish a coherent and consistent set of requirements and verification processes to support over 400 detailed design work packages.

A traditional Systems Engineering approach of providing each work package with its set of requirements documents would not have been an efficient method to provide the 63,834 unique verification results. Such a traditional approach is vulnerable to inconsistency across work packages, and it does not allow for adaptation to changes in the program. Ultimately, a traditional approach would have diminished the effectiveness of the Technical Assurance process. Therefore, a MBSE approach was implemented, which built a Master Data set with a taxonomy of Object Types and requirements allocated per Object Type. This process is summarised in Figure 1. The Master Data set was developed based on inputs from the discipline leads and the ontology used in the client asset management system. It was validated by the Engineering Director.

Figure 1: Process of categorising Object Types and allocating requirements - HS2

The project used 60 different Object Types in the Master Data set to define assets, and then allocated requirements to those Object Types. A Taxonomy was implemented on the Object Types: for example,

in Figure 1, a Viaduct is a specialisation of an Underbridge, which is a specialisation of a Bridging Structure. By allocating requirements to Bridging Structures, the project was able to apply those requirements to all Under bridges and Viaducts, since these were also classified as Bridging Structures.

The project developed standardised verification plans based on this method of requirement allocation. It pushed that information to over 4,000 civil assets in the project based on their Object Type classification. By linking the assets to work packages and allocating requirements by Object Types, the project achieved consistency in requirements allocation and verification results. For example, each of the 15 Viaducts would be classified as a Viaduct and as such, they would have the same allocated requirements, regardless of the work package they were in.

In addition to improved consistency, the Object Type approach also enabled some degree of automated verification. If for a given work package there were no assets of a certain object type (e.g., no viaducts), then the system would automatically generate a verification statement that states that the requirement was not applicable, and it would provide a justification (e.g., this requirement relates to viaducts and there are no viaducts in this package). This approach also improved flexibility and adaptability and the approach made it easier to cascade changes to any of the assets and work packages.

The methodology was supported by using the Systems Engineering model (SEm[®]), an ontology based on ISO 15926 principles [ISO 2018]. The Systems Engineering model was used to configure the Relatics low-code web application, which enables non-technical users to interact with semantic models. This implementation enabled the management of the vast number of requirements and verification processes involved in this project. Linking requirements with assets provided a flexible way to handle changes in the delivery program.

Establishing a Master Data set approach to MBSE worked exceptionally at the contract level. The approach allowed for all the design teams to access the requirements and complete the verification for their work packages. It improved quality and saved time. As the allocation of unique assets to work packages changed based on construction schedules, the requirements, verification and validation was able to adaptively and flexibly respond.

However, due to the contracting approach of the broader HS2 programme, the processes outlined above were only applied within the one contract. Within one contract, there was no need for standardised Master Data between different delivery entities across projects. Furthermore, when the project commenced in 2017, the use of appropriate Linked Data tooling was not present in the market. Consequently, the Master Data and Object Types were not published in Linked Data libraries and so there was further potential to enrich the MBSE process using Linked Data.

Flemish Tunnel Standard

The Flemish Agency for roads and traffic needs to renovate 20 important tunnels in Flanders to comply to the European standards for Tunnel safety. To achieve this, there was a need for a Flemish Tunnel Standard - "Vlaamse Tunnelstandaard" (VTSa) in Dutch - to provide consistent technical assurance over the 20 projects.

Two of the renovation projects had already commenced prior to the development of the VTSa. Without the VTSa, these tunnels were initially designed to a combination of the existing National

Tunnel Standard “Landelijke Tunnelstandaard” (LTS) and the requirements set out by Lantis (the Belgian public agency responsible infrastructure in the Flanders region), and later designed to the requirements listed in the VTSa. The development of the VTSa was progressed per system part. For each tunnel part used on a project, it was first necessary to check if that part was available in the most recent baseline of the VTSa. When the VTSa was not available for that tunnel part, the projects used the Lantis set, or if that was also unavailable, the LTS.

The decision was made to move to an MBSE approach, like HS2, but enriched by employing Master Data Libraries using Linked Data. The HS2 approach to MBSE on the contract worked independently from the other contractors (e.g., other civils contractors and the rail systems contractors have different ways of managing technical assurance). By contrast, on the Flemish Tunnel Standard, each tunnel contractor is working to the progressively updated VTSa. This organisational environment presents a greater benefit for a Master Data Library approach (rather than an isolated Master Data set). Consequently, the VTSa is progressively updated and published using Linked Data. It is also worth reiterating that when the HS2 project was commenced in 2017, Linked Data was not as common within the industry as it is today.

Relatics was previously employed on HS2, but it did not support the creation and publication of Linked Data. It is therefore supplemented here with Laces, to allow non-technical users to create and share Master Data Libraries in Linked Data. This allows projects to select the required objects from the OTL and subsequently, object-by-object, select the relevant version of requirements that they have agreed to. As all publications can be subject to new versions, this tool also allows for connection to a specific publication version. In this way, it is possible to always use the latest version of the VTSa and OTL, or to stick to a specific version of the LTS and Lantis, as they are all published separately. This process is summarised in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Process of categorising Object Types and allocating requirements -Flemish Tunnel Standard

Results

The implementation of the Object Type MBSE methodology on the HS2 project using Relatics resulted in several benefits which are critical to the continued success of the project. Firstly, the object-type approach improved consistency of requirements across the (currently) 486 packages of work. This

meant that all assets of the same type had the same requirements across each work package. The approach also provided greater flexibility and adaptability. 148 new packages have been created to date in response to changing construction schedules, and by using the Object Type Master Data approach, requirements can be allocated to work packages by selecting the assets to be included in each package. Verification has been similarly improved. Using the Object Type Master Data approach, over 23% of the scheme design requirements were automatically verified. For a project of the scale and magnitude of HS2, this amounts to a significant amount of time saved. Overall, the implementation of the Object Type approach to MBSE on HS2 demonstrated a strong case for its continued application on other complex engineering projects.

The addition of Linked Data and the change from Master Data to Master Data Libraries, such as Object Type Libraries provided many further benefits. Utilising Linked Data required an augmented set of tooling, and as such, Laces was introduced. Once Master Data Libraries were published, the accessibility of information across many projects facilitated the collaboration and coordination among stakeholders, enabling them to work together efficiently and effectively. Laces also provided a more effective means of baselining requirements and managing version control.

When an individual tunnel project found a lesson learned, the requirements associated with a particular tunnel system component were updated in the VTSa Master Data. As the VTSa was shared with the remaining projects, the lessons from one project systematically made their way into other projects. On HS2, by contrast, sharing lessons learned between projects required the contractor to inform the HS2 organisation (by correspondence such as RFI), who would then have to pass the information to other contractors. The process of sharing and improving from iterative lessons learned was therefore facilitated by the MBSE process on the Flemish Tunnel, unlike on HS2, through the publishing of Master Data Libraries using Linked Data.

Conclusion

The HS2 project has demonstrated that MBSE can be significantly enriched by using Master Data and Object Types. The Flemish Tunnel Standard has then shown that this enrichment can be further enhanced using Linked data to create Libraries of Master Data and Object Types. These methods have helped to streamline the complex management of requirements by ensuring consistency, enabling automation, improving collaboration between stakeholders and ultimately, contributing to the successful execution of both projects.

On HS2, a MBSE approach was implemented which built a Master Data set with a taxonomy of Object Types. Requirements were then allocated per Object Type. By linking the assets to work packages and allocating requirements by Object Types, the project achieved consistency in requirements allocation and verification results. This meant that all assets of the same type had the same requirements across each work package. In addition to ensuring consistency (and thus quality), the process was also more efficient, enabling automated verification and saving a significant amount of time.

On the Flemish Tunnel Standard, the approach was further improved by utilising Linked Data principles to create Master Data Libraries that could be shared across projects. The choice and use of a standardised ontology across the supply chain was found to be key for the effective implementation of OTLs across projects. This approach required additional tooling, and so Laces was introduced to supplement Relatics. This approach enabled more effective publishing of requirements and version

control, enabling different stakeholders to use different sets of requirements. Ultimately, the Flemish Tunnel Standard both reiterated key benefits and highlighted new further possibilities associated with enriching MBSE with Master Data.

Nevertheless, it is important to note that while the Object Type approach has proven to be effective in these projects, there is still a need for more initiatives to replicate its use and further advance its development. Thus, we call for more organisations to explore the potential benefits of the Object Type approach in MBSE, and to continue to share their findings to further advance this methodology.

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